

Synthesis of substituted *s*-triazine derivatives and studies of their antimicrobial activities

L. M. Patel, K. H. Chikhalia and P. S. Desai*

Department of Chemistry, B. K. M. Science College, Valsad-396 001, India

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Some new *s*-triazine derivatives have been synthesised. These compounds act as anti-bacterial, fungal and tubercular agents.

A number of pharmacological properties viz. antibacterial, anticoagulant, stimulant, vasodilatory, antiallergic and antifungal activities have been reported for a variety of coumarin derivatives. Some substituted coumarin derivatives have good antibacterial activities¹. Imidazole derivatives are effective drugs against hypertension, have good antibacterial and analgesic activity and reported exhibiting hypotensive properties. Some substituted imidazole derivatives have been prepared and used as antidiabetics, antihypertensive, antilipidemic and blood platelet aggregation inhibitors².

Results and discussion

4-Methyl-7-hydroxy coumarin was condensed with 2,4,6-trichloro-*s*-triazine, which was further condensed with 2-methyl-5-nitro imidazole and the later on condensed with various aryl thiourea.

The physical and analytical data are presented in Table 1. Antibacterial activity of the compounds were determined by Agar diffusion method³. The results are presented in Table 2. Among the compounds **4b** was found to be most active against both *S. paratyphi B.* and *Enterobactor*. The compound **4i** was found to be most active against *E. coil*, *S. paratyphi B.* and *P. vulgaris*. The compound **4f** was found to be most active against *S. aureus*. Antitubercular activity of the compound was determined by tube dilution technique⁴. The results are presented in Table 3. Among the compounds **3c** was found to be most active against H₃₇R_v strain of *M. tuberculosis*. Antifungal study reveals that compound **3c** was found to be most active against *C. albicans*.

Experimental

All the chemicals (A.R. grade) were purified by recrystallisation or distillation before use. The purity of the compound was judged by TLC using benzene and methanol as solvent and from their C, H and N analyses. M.ps. were determined in open capillaries using a Toshniwal appa-

where, Ar = C₆H₅ (**4a**), 4-O₂NC₆H₄ (**4b**),

2-ClC₆H₄ (**4c**), 3-ClC₆H₄ (**4d**), 4-ClC₆H₄ (**4e**),

2-H₃CC₆H₄ (**4f**), 3-H₃CC₆H₄ (**4g**),

4-H₃CC₆H₄ (**4h**), 2-H₃COC₆H₄ (**4i**),

4-H₃COC₆H₄ (**4j**), 1-C₁₀H₇ (**4k**)

ratus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and NMR spectra (DMSO) on a Varian model EM-360 L spectrophotometer using TMS as internal reference.

4-Methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin was prepared according to literature⁵. Yield 85% (m.p. 182°C).

Table 1							
Compd.	Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
4a	C ₆ H ₅	162	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₈ O ₅ S	54.10 (54.33)	3.37 (3.39)	20.10 (21.13)
b	4-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	119	62	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₉ O ₇ S	49.90 (50.08)	2.91 (2.95)	21.95 (21.91)
c	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	124	60	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₈ O ₅ ClS	50.80 (51.01)	2.98 (3.01)	19.80 (19.84)
d	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	169	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₈ O ₅ ClS	50.80 (51.01)	2.91 (3.01)	19.79 (19.84)
e	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	190	68	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₈ O ₅ ClS	50.79 (51.01)	2.98 (3.01)	19.88 (19.84)
f	2-H ₃ CC ₆ H ₄	220	70	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₅ S	54.95 (55.14)	3.68 (3.67)	20.52 (20.58)
g	3-H ₃ CC ₆ H ₄	115	66	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₅ S	54.89 (55.14)	3.63 (3.67)	20.53 (20.58)
h	4-H ₃ CC ₆ H ₄	245	62	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₅ S	55.54 (55.14)	3.69 (3.67)	20.54 (20.58)
i	2-H ₃ COC ₆ H ₄	310	63	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₆ S	53.35 (53.57)	3.53 (3.57)	19.95 (20.00)
j	4-H ₃ COC ₆ H ₄	205	65	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₆ S	53.35 (53.57)	3.59 (3.57)	19.97 (20.00)
k	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	159	70	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₈ O ₆ S	57.69 (57.93)	3.41 (3.44)	19.28 (19.31)

Table 2						
Compd.	Ar	Zone of inhibition in mm at 50 µg/ml				
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. paratyphi B.</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>Enterobacter</i>
4a	C ₆ H ₅	–	–	6	4	6
b	4-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	6	–	7	–	7
c	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	–	7	–	7
d	3-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	–	6	4	6
e	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	–	4	6	–	6
f	2-H ₃ CC ₆ H ₄	–	8	6	6	6
g	3-H ₃ CC ₆ H ₄	–	–	7	6	7
h	4-H ₃ CC ₆ H ₄	–	6	6	–	6
i	2-H ₃ CC ₆ H ₄	8	–	6	7	6
j	4-H ₃ CO ₆ H ₄	–	–	6	–	6
k	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	–	–	6	–	6
Standard drugs		Organisms			Zone of inhibition in mm at 25 µg/ml	
Phexine		<i>Enterobacter</i>			18	
Norfloxacin		<i>E. coli</i>			18	
Althrocine		<i>S. aureus</i>			12	
Sperfloxacine		<i>S. paratyphi B.</i>			16	
Tetracycline		<i>P. vulgaris</i>			14	

Table 3

Compd.	Ar.	Antitubercular activity	
		H ₃₇ R _v strain of <i>M. tuberculosis</i> (µg/ml)	Antifungal activity <i>C. albicans</i> (µg/ml)
4a	C ₆ H ₄	200	–
b	4-O ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	–	–
c	2-ClC ₆ H ₄	50	50
e	4-ClC ₆ H ₂	100	100
h	4-H ₃ CC ₆ H ₄	200	–
j	4-H ₃ COC ₆ H ₄	–	100
k	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	200	200

2-(4-Methylcoumarin-7-yloxy)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine :

To a stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (9.22 g, 0.05 mol) in acetone at 0–5°C, the solution of 4-methyl-7-hydroxy coumarin (8.0 g, 0.05 mol) in acetone was added and the pH was maintained around by the addition of 10% NaHCO₃ solution. The stirring was continued at the same temperature (0–5°C) for 4 h. After completion of the reaction stirring was stopped and the solution was treated with crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol. Yield 80%, m.p. 235°C.

2-(4-Methylcoumarin-7-yloxy)-4-(2-methyl-5-nitroimidazol-1-yl)-6-chloro-s-triazine :

To a stirred solution of 2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole (6.35 g, 0.05 mol) in acetone at 35–45°C, the solution of 2-(4-methyl coumarin-7-yloxy)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (16.2 g, 0.005 mol) in acetone was added and the pH was maintained neutral by the addition of 10% NaHCO₃ solution. The stirring was continued at the same temperature (35–45°C) for 4 h. After completion of the reaction the stirring was stopped and the solution was treated with crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol. Yield 70%, m.p. 279°C.

2-(4-Methylcoumarin-7-yloxy)-4-(2-methyl-5-nitroimidazol-1-yl)-6-(arylthioureido)-s-triazine (4a-k) :

To a mixture of 2-(4-methyl coumarin-7-yloxy)-4-(2-methyl-5-nitroimidazol-1-yl)-6-chloro-s-triazine (0.4145 g, 0.001 mol) and phenyl thiourea (0.152 g, 0.001 mol) in acetone (40 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 h on a water-bath at 80–90°C. The pH was maintained neutral by the addition of 10% NaHCO₃ solution. After completion of the reaction the reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and water. The solid obtained was filtered, dried and crystallised from absolute alcohol. Yield 65%, m.p. 4a, 162°; b, 119°; c, 124°; d, 169°; e, 162°; f, 220°; g, 115°; h, 245°; i, 310°; j, 205°; k, 159°C.

ν_{\max} (4b), 1730 cm⁻¹ (C=O stretching in α -pyrone ring),

1576 cm⁻¹ (C=S stretching in thioureido linkage), 3427 cm⁻¹ (N–H stretching in 2° amine), 3084 cm⁻¹ (C–H stretching in imidazole ring), 854 cm⁻¹ (=C–N- stretching in nitro compound), 1365 cm⁻¹ (>N- stretching in 3° amine, imidazole ring), 812 cm⁻¹ (*p*-substituted benzene).

(4e) 1732 cm⁻¹ (C=O stretching in α -pyrone ring), 1579 cm⁻¹ (C=S stretching in thioureido linkage), 3438 cm⁻¹ (N–H stretching in 2° amine), 3084 cm⁻¹ (C–H stretching in imidazole ring), 1015 cm⁻¹ (=C–Cl stretching in aryl chloride), 1365 cm⁻¹ (>N- stretching in 3° amine, imidazole ring), 806 cm⁻¹ (*p*-substituted benzene).

(4h) 1732 cm⁻¹ (>C=O) stretching in α -pyrone ring), 1579 cm⁻¹ (>C=S stretching in thioureido linkage), 3438 cm⁻¹ (N–H stretching in 2° amine), 3084 cm⁻¹ (C–H stretching in imidazole ring), 1365 cm⁻¹ (>N- stretching in 3° amine, imidazole ring), 1616 cm⁻¹ (C=N stretching in imidazole, skeletal band), 806 cm⁻¹ (*p*-substituted benzene), 2925 cm⁻¹ (C–H, (asym) stretching in methyl group), 2855 cm⁻¹ (C–H, (sym) stretching in methyl group).

(4a) δ 2.21 (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 6.4 (1H, s, benzopyrane ring), 6.672 (1H, s, NH), 7.3–8.0 (9H, m, Ar-H).

(4b) δ 2.22 (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 6.42 (1H, s, benzopyrane ring), 6.68 (1H, s, NH), 7.35–8.03 (8H, m, Ar-H).

(4d) δ 2.2 (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 6.42 (1H, s, benzopyrane ring), 6.67 (1H, s, NH), 7.3–7.9 (8H, m, Ar-H).

(4g) δ 1.89 (3H, s, (CH₃)), 2.12 (8H, s, (CH₃)₂), 6.41 (1H, s, benzopyrane ring), 6.67 (1H, s, NH), 7.4–7.8 (8H, m, Ar-H).

(4j) δ 2.1 (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 3.74 (1H, s, OCH₃), 6.43, (1H, s, benzopyrane ring), 7.1–7.9 (8H, m, Ar-H).

(4k) δ 2.18 (6H, s, (CH₃)₂), 6.42 (1H, s, benzopyrane ring), 6.62 (1H, s, NH), 7.1–8.2 (12H, m, Ar-H).

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